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Ethics Advisor

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

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Ethics Advisor

Minimum Viable Skills Profile

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Ethics Advisors focuses on the critical competencies required by professionals responsible for upholding ethical standards within Open Science. **Ethics Advisors play a vital role in ensuring that research practices align with ethical principles** while promoting openness, transparency, and adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). These professionals are often tasked with balancing ethical considerations with the objectives of Open Science, including data sharing, collaboration, and accessibility, while mitigating risks related to societal, legal, and moral responsibilities.

The term “Ethics Advisor” includes professionals such as Data Ethicists, Ethics Officers, and members of Ethics Committees. These roles may vary across research institutions and projects, but all share the responsibility of ensuring that ethical guidelines are met. Ethics Advisors provide guidance on a range of issues, including research involving AI systems, dual-use technologies, animal experimentation, and broader societal impacts. They help anticipate and address potential ethical dilemmas, ensuring that research activities respect fundamental values such as accountability, transparency, inclusivity, and respect for diversity.

A key responsibility of Ethics Advisors is promoting ethical decision-making in research, while fostering a culture of openness. This includes navigating the ethical challenges posed by data protection, privacy, and the responsible use of research data. **Ethics Advisors work closely with researchers, Legal Experts, and Data Protection Officers (DPOs)** to create environments where ethical principles and legal compliance coexist. They provide critical input on ethical reviews, draft policies, and offer advice on complex issues such as dual-use technologies and the societal implications of scientific advancements.

In their work, Ethics Advisors promote Openness, FAIRness, and the ethical principles of responsibility/accountability, transparency, pluralism, and respect/inclusion in the realization of Open Science within the context of research projects and organizations. **Their mission is to promote accountability, transparency, and inclusivity in research, while also safeguarding against ethical risks.**

ETHICS ADVISOR

Ethics Advisors play a critical role in ensuring that research practices, particularly in the context of Open Science, align with ethical standards and principles. Their primary responsibility is to promote ethical decision-making and compliance with ethical guidelines while addressing issues such as privacy, data protection, and societal impacts. Ethics Advisors navigate ethical complexities, particularly in areas involving sensitive data, AI systems, and dual-use technologies, while fostering openness and accountability. Their expertise is essential in balancing the ethical obligations required to safeguard research participants and broader societal interests, while also promoting openness and compliance with the FAIR principles.

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Ethics Officer, Data Protection Officer, Data Ethicist, Ethics Expert, Members of Ethics Committees.

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Good understanding of OS and its practices.
 - Ability to establish the appropriate strategy, frameworks and course of actions to foster and enhance OS.
 - Expert knowledge of the FAIR principles and how to apply them (e.g. publishing research data in a way that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
 - Ability to identify ethical issues, raise awareness and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles (eg transparency and accountability), frameworks (e.g. RRI Framework) and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (e.g. European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – ALLEA and the OECD's Best Practices for Ensuring Scientific Integrity and Preventing Misconduct).
 - Ability to identify and address ethical issues related to personal data governance during all the data lifecycle, including but not limited to the management of personal data (e.g. collecting, storing and sharing), development and management of related policies, and knowledge of the applicable regulations on privacy and personal data protection that may concern to ethical aspects.
- Ability to raise awareness and provide instructions on (research) data ethics, and whenever needed, on specific scenarios and fields of research (e.g. in case of using data-driven technologies, this may include an expert knowledge on the rules provided in the Artificial Intelligence Act and related regulations and knowledge of best practices related to avoiding bias in data processing).
 - Ability to establish connections and ease communication between different players (e.g. researchers) and bodies (e.g. legal department and the research ethics committees) when addressing ethical issues.
 - Knowledge of the necessary resources to raise awareness and advise on the ethical use and management of intellectual property rights and non-personal data.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

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|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership • Effective communication • Stakeholder engagement and networking • Management skills | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical and Analytical thinking • Collaboration • Sharing knowledge and processes |
|---|--|

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Map and identify ethical concerns inside the organization/ research project.
- Advise the organization on the compatibility of local practices with ethical principles and the existing frameworks and codes of conduct (eg FAIR, CARE principles, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, RRI framework).
- Advocate for pluralism and inclusion in Open Science.
- Set up policies, guidelines and other instruments necessary to the realization of the ethical principles concerning OS.
- Interact with stakeholders in order to ensure that research is being conducted in a responsible and transparent manner, and that consider all stakeholders rights and interests.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- Raised awareness of the ethical principles in open research through the interaction with stakeholders, and advocacy activities.
- Main ethical issues are addressed in the practice of Open Science in the relevant context e.g. the organization or research project.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve problems](#); [Identify problems](#); [Show initiative](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Address an audience](#); [Advise others](#); [Motivate others](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Plan](#); [Time management](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Think creatively](#); [Manage time](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#).

ResearchComp: [Strategic thinking](#); [Systemic thinking](#); [Interact professionally](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#); [Data-driven decision management](#); [Information security](#); [Resource management](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Media relations](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Engagement](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Knowledge brokering](#).

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